

REINCARNATE

D4.2 – A Set of Methods for Economic and Ecological Appraisal of Circular Economy Innovations

D4.2 A Set of Methods for Economic and Ecological Appraisal of Circular Economy Innovations

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Abstract

Adoption of circular economy approaches will depend on their financial-economic viability as well as their environmental benefits. In this report, we provide an overview of appraisal methods to incorporate both the value of materials at end-of-use cycles and the environmental performance in support of investment decisions. Standard models for Net Present Value (NPV) calculation to inform investment decisions in buildings do not take into account the residual value (end of use cycle) value of materials or that circular building components can have multiple use cycles. More advanced NPV models that do take into account residual material values and multiple use cycles have been developed at theoretical level. However, their practical application is hampered by lack of reliable data to underpin assumptions about the development of material values and number of use cycles. Moreover, discounting of material values over decades reduces the impact and relevance of these values at the start of use cycles of buildings. Therefore, it is recommended to 1) build a database about material values and building component reuse, 2) use NPV calculations a couple of years before the decision to disassemble (parts) of a building, when it becomes relevant to assess potential proceedings from building materials and components (the report also points at how methods for condition assessment and NPV calculation incorporated in the CP-IM model can support such assessments), and 3) conduct Life Cycle Assessments (LCA) to assess the environmental impacts in addition to NPV calculations.

Keywords

Net Present Value, Environmental Cost Indicator, Total Cost of Ownership, Life Cycle Costing, Life Cycle Analysis, Circular, Buildings, Components, Materials

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
DCF	Discounted Cash Flow
NPV	Net Present Value
CE	Circular Economy
CE-LCC	Circular Life Cycle Costing
CDW	Construction and Demolition Waste
CP-IM	Circular Potential Information Platform
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
TCO	Total Costs of Ownership

Reincarnate project

The average lifespan of a building is 39 years — in Europe, it is only 25-30 years — and the main reason for demolition is obsolescence. This is why there is a large amount of construction and demolition waste (CDW) — representing approximately 25-30% of all waste in Europe —, in addition to that generated in current construction works.

The recycling rate for CDW is relatively high (above 75%). This activity generated \$126.89 billion in 2019 — Europe contributed the largest share, almost two-fifths of the total global market — and is projected to reach \$149.19 billion by 2027. Unfortunately, many of the most valuable materials in CDW cannot be meaningfully separated and end up in landfills.

This helps to get an idea of the efficiency potential for climate neutrality that exists in construction.

Reincarnate aims at advancing circular economy practices within the European construction industry and enabling to significantly maximise the life cycle of buildings, construction products and materials, reduce CDW by 80%, increase the reusability of buildings, construction products and materials and, as a result, lower the sector's emissions by 70%.

As a result of these actions, Reincarnate will significantly advance circular economy practices within the European construction industry.

First, it will create a Circular Potential Information Management (CP-IM) platform and a set of innovations to use it. These solutions will draw upon emerging digital technologies, such as digital twin representation, artificial intelligence, and robotic automation.

3 empirically proven social science insights will allow fostering widespread adoption of reused high-quality construction products and materials, and business eco-system development frameworks to combine actors within sustainable value chains. All innovations will be demonstrated on eleven selected real-world projects and value chains. Furthermore, business process guidelines and an e-learning platform will be developed to drive the dissemination and exploitation of the Reincarnate results.

Contents

1. Introduction	9
2. Financial-economic appraisal	10
2.1. Financial-economic appraisal principles.....	10
2.2. Valuation building at beginning of use cycle.....	11
2.2.1. Building costs	12
2.2.2. Maintenance costs.....	12
2.2.3. Lifespan.....	12
2.2.4. Residual value	12
2.3. Valuation building components at beginning of use cycle	15
2.4. Valuation building and components at end of use cycle	17
3. Supporting methods for assessing circular potential	20
3.1. Level of disassembly.....	20
3.2. Service life	21
3.3. Condition assessment.....	21
3.4. Integration of probabilistic life-cycle assessment.....	22
4. Wider perceptions of value	27
4.1. Cultural and social factors.....	27
4.2. Circularity appraisal in certification systems.....	28
4.2.1. BREEAM	28
4.2.2. DGNB	29
4.2.3. LEED	29
5. Ecological Appraisal	31
5.1. Life cycle assessment.....	31
5.2. Global warming potential and abiotic depletion potential.....	32
5.3. Whole life carbon and building life cycle stages	34
5.4. CO2 reporting on waste management	35

D4.2 A Set of Methods for Economic and Ecological Appraisal of Circular Economy Innovations

5.5. Integrating LCA and LCC.....	37
6. Integration into CP-IM.....	40
6.1. End-of-lifetime Implementation in LCC.....	41
6.2. Condition Assessment Integration.....	42
7. Conclusion	43
References	45

1. Introduction

Adoption of circular economy approaches will depend on their financial-economic viability as well as their environmental benefits. In this report, we describe appraisal methods to incorporate the value of materials at end-of-use cycles and the environmental performance in appraisal of buildings.

In chapter 2 we focus on how circularity can be incorporated into Net Present Value (NPV) calculations, with a particular emphasis on residual (end-of-use cycle) values of building components.

For incorporation of the residual value of building components in NPV calculations it is necessary to assess the costs of disassembly as well as the re-use potential. Therefore, in chapter 3 we discuss some supporting methods for assessing the circular potential of building components.

Whilst NPV calculations are commonly used to calculate financial-economic values, particularly from an investor's perspective, the value that people and organisations attach to circularity in buildings is also subject to a complex set of social and cultural factors that influence the perception of value. Some of these are discussed in chapter 4, also reflecting on certification systems that are used by investors to incorporate environmental performance in their investment decisions.

In chapter 5 we turn to ecological appraisal methods, Life Cycle Assessment, and reflect on how they can incorporate circularity and (in theory) be combined with Life Cycle Costing methods.

Finally, in chapter 6, we summarize our conclusions and in chapter 7 we describe how some of the methods are incorporated in Reincarnate's CP-IM module.

2. Financial-economic appraisal

Adoption of circular economy approaches will depend on their financial-economic viability as well as their environmental benefits. In this chapter, we discuss approaches to incorporate circularity in the assessment of the financial-economic value of buildings.

2.1. Financial-economic appraisal principles

Financial-economic appraisal for investment decisions in buildings commonly encompass market valuation and/or estimations of the return on investment and/or (total) costs of ownership.

The market value is an estimation of the best price that could be achieved when a building is offered on the market, either in use or free of use. Market valuation is most commonly based on the comparison of recent transactions of similar buildings sold at similar locations. Return on investment is most commonly based on Net Present Value (NPV), also referred to as Discounted Cashflow (DCF), calculations taking into account future, expected, income and expenditure stemming from the construction and exploitation of the building. Particularly if a building does not generate significant revenue streams, because it is used for own or public purposes, the NPV calculations focus on the expenditure and can then be referred to as Total Costs of Ownership (TCO).

From a strictly financial-economic point of view, an investor is willing to buy a (new or existing) building if the costs of acquiring the building are lower than or equal to the value that the investor attaches to the building. Likewise, an owner will consider selling a building if the market value equals or is higher than the value that the owner attaches to the building.

The above principles lead to two basic mechanisms through which circularity can influence the financial-economic appraisal, and these mechanisms are not mutually exclusive. In the first mechanism, circularity itself leads to a premium for investors. This can for example happen if circularity becomes conditional in building regulations or circularity becomes an important aspect in the governance of investors. The growing demand for circular buildings can then result in relatively higher transaction prices, which will in turn be reflected in the appraisal of market values (see also Chapter 4).

In the second mechanism, circularity is taken into account in the NPV calculations, for example because it leads to different construction costs, maintenance expenditure and/or costs and revenues at the end of the use-life of buildings.

With the basic principles described above in mind, we will now discuss how circularity can be taken into account in financial-economic appraisal of buildings and building components, emphasising NPV based methods (the 'second mechanism'). In doing so, we will specify how circularity can be taken into account in valuation of:

- buildings (section 2.2) and building components (section 2.3) at the beginning of a use cycle, which can support decisions in investing in 'circular' buildings;
- buildings and building components at the end of the financial-economic lifespan, which can support decisions on circular disassembly and reuse (section 2.4).

2.2. Valuation building at beginning of use cycle

If an investor has to make a decision about acquiring a new, to be constructed, building, the decision will be positive if the Net Present Value of income and expenditure that is expected to be generated with the building in the future equals or is higher than the costs of acquiring the building, including the land. In a formula the NPV calculation for an investment decision can be depicted as follows:

$$NPV = -IC_0 + \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{I_t - E_t}{(1+i)^t} + \frac{RV_n}{(1+i)^n}$$

- IC_0 = initial Investment Costs
 I_t = Income in period 't'
 E_t = Expenditure in period 't'
 RV_n = Residual Value at end of period
 i = discount rate
 n = number of periods

Circularity can influence various parameters in the NPV calculation: the initial building costs, maintenance expenditure, the lifespan and the residual value.

2.2.1. Building costs

There can be additional and/or reduced building costs due to circular design, construction and material choice. For example, higher construction costs can occur if relatively commonly available materials are replaced by more circular, but at the moment also more uncommon and scarcely available (e.g. biobased) materials. Construction costs can also increase if the construction process is more complicated because different connections are used to facilitate future disassembly, or if a lot of effort has to be put into finding and certifying reclaimed materials. On the other hand, construction costs could also decrease, if detachability is combined with industrial production and/or if reclaimed materials can be obtained relatively cheap.

2.2.2. Maintenance costs

There can be additional and/or reduced maintenance costs due to circularity. If the design takes into account easy maintenance and/or durability as one of the aspects of circularity, maintenance costs can be lower. Alternatively, the use of reclaimed or biobased materials could in some cases also lead to higher maintenance costs.

2.2.3. Lifespan

If durability of materials and/or adaptability/flexibility of the building for changing use is taken into account as part of circular design, this could in theory lead to a longer lifespan of (structural) elements of the building.

2.2.4. Residual value

Circularity itself calls for a more elaborated look at the value of the building at the end-of-use-cycle, represented by the residual value in the NPV formula. In line with the principles described above, the financial-economic end of life of a building is reached when the market value of alternative use of the land is higher than:

- the value of the building in its current use
- and the value of putting the building to alternative uses, possibly after renovation/transformation (adaptive reuse) (see Figure 2.1).

The latter makes it important to assess alternative uses (adaptive reuse) to understand if the financial-economic lifespan has indeed come to an end. If the value of putting the

D4.2 A Set of Methods for Economic and Ecological Appraisal of Circular Economy Innovations

building to alternative use is higher than the value of the building in current use, the functional lifespan of the building ends in financial-economic terms, but not necessarily the financial-economic lifespan of the building itself. That happens when both value in current use or with alternative uses are lower than the market value of the land.

Figure 1.1: financial-economic lifespan ends when market value meets residual value (see also Conijn, 1995)

If we follow this principle from a traditional linear economy perspective, the residual value at the end of the financial-economic lifespan equals the market value of the land 'empty of use', minus the (demolition) costs of clearing the land for a new use.

However, if we follow the principle from a circular economy perspective, the residual value at the end of the financial-economic lifespan equals the market value of land, minus the costs of disassembly of the building into reclaimable components plus revenues of the re-usable materials.

Thus, if the residual value is calculated from a circular economy perspective, the higher value at the end of the financial-economic lifespan of the building may compensate for higher upfront costs. The end of the financial-economic lifespan is usually decades from the initial investment decision, so the effect of the higher residual value will be heavily discounted, even if material prices rise considerably. Zweste (2023), for example, did a simple sensitivity analysis showing that an additional residual market value in 50 years will have almost no impact on the NPV, as it will only count for 3% to a max of 9%, depending on the discount rate (see Figure 2.2).

D4.2 A Set of Methods for Economic and Ecological Appraisal of Circular Economy Innovations

Figure 2.2: NPV after 50 years as percentage of cashflow in first year at different discount rates (IRR) (Zwueste, 2023)

There is also an interesting paradox in the circular economy approach towards the calculation of the residual value, being that if the value of re-useable materials rises then the financial-economic lifespan of the building could end sooner (see Figure 2.3).

Figure 3.2: financial-economic lifespan can shorten when residual value is higher

In practice, NPV calculations normally take into account a holding period (10-15 years) that is shorter than the expected financial-economic lifespan of a building. Thus, the residual value at the end of the financial-economic lifespan is hardly ever directly taken into account in NPV calculations. Indirectly, it can be taken into account in the estimation of the market value at the end of the holding period. One way to do that is to make an estimation of the residual value of the building components, to which we will turn in the next section.

2.3. Valuation building components at beginning of use cycle

In a circular economy approach towards valuation, the financial-economic appraisal of the residual value of building components and materials becomes a factor. There are two basic approaches for estimating the value of building components: based on a single use cycle and based on multiple use cycles.

In the first and most straight forward approach the residual value of the building components is based on the current market value, corrected with a price index and a depreciation factor (for 'ageing'), minus costs for salvation of the building components. The sum of the residual values of the individual building components can then be used as a basis for the calculation of the total residual value of the building – as explained in the previous section.

There are several practical challenges in determining the residual value of building components. First, it will be very hard to estimate the salvation costs of each individual building component, if the salvation is part of a disassembly of the wider building. The question then becomes what salvation costs to allocate to the individual building components whilst many of the salvation costs are made for the overall disassembly of the building. If the main purpose of the valuation is to estimate the residual value of the whole building, there is a practical way around this, and that is by estimating the residual value of the building components separately from the overall disassembly costs. The NPV formula can then be depicted as follows:

$$RV_0 = \frac{RCa \times (1 + p_a - d_a)^n}{(1 + i)^n} + \frac{RCb \times (1 + p_b - d_b)^n}{(1 + i)^n} + \dots + \frac{RCz \times (1 + p_z - d_z)^n}{(1 + i)^n} - \frac{DC_n}{(1 + i)^n}$$

RV_0 = NPV Residual Value building as sum of residual value components

DC_n = Disassembly Costs at end of period

$RC_{a,b,\dots,z}$ = Residual value Component a, b, etc.

i = discount rate

n = number of periods

p = price index component a, b, etc.

d = depreciation factor component a, b, etc.

D4.2 A Set of Methods for Economic and Ecological Appraisal of Circular Economy Innovations

Another, both theoretical and practical, challenge is that building components have different use spans. Whilst some building components may be replaced multiple times over the lifespan of a building, others might last as long as the building itself. To deal with this challenge, a second approach for valuation of building components has been developed: the Circular Economy Life Cycle Costing (CE-LCC) approach, developed by Jansen et al. (2020). This method can be used to calculate the Life Cycle Cost (or Total Costs of Ownership) of a product that consists of multiple parts which have different use- and lifespans. In this approach, the LCC of the product equals the sum of the LCC of the individual parts, whilst taking into account:

- different scenarios for the amount of parts that are expected to be re-used after use-cycles;
- different scenarios for the refurbishment and remanufacturing costs that are necessary to reuse parts in a next use cycle;
- the final disposal costs when parts reach the end of their use cycles and thus their 'end of life'.

In a (simplified) NPV formula, this approach can be depicted as follows (see Jansen et al. (2020) for a full and more detailed description of the method and its application to a circular kitchen).

$$CE - LCC = -IC_{a,0} - IC_{b,0} - \dots - IC_{z,0} - \sum_{t=1}^{n-1} \frac{EC_{a,t} + EC_{b,t} + \dots + EC_{z,t}}{(1+i)^t} + RV_0$$

CE-LCC = NPV sum of costs and residual value components

$IC_{x,0}$ = Initial investment Costs component 'x'

$EC_{x,t}$ = net Expenditure for removal, refurbishment, (re)installation and replacement of Component 'x' in period 't'

RV_0 = NPV Residual Value building as sum of residual value components (see above)

i = discount rate

n = number of periods

All of the described methods, and in particular the method developed by Jansen et al. (2020), although in theory correct, require a lot of assumptions about the development of the market value of the building components (price indices, depreciation factor, salvation costs, refurbishment rates and costs, etc.), which on the one hand makes relying on the outcomes risky and therefore unattractive for investors. On the other hand, they could provide additional comfort if the calculations indeed show an upward potential of the residual value, even under cautious estimations, compared to the normal linear approach.

2.4. Valuation building and components at end of use cycle

From a circular economy perspective, it is not only important to focus on financial-economic appraisal for new 'circular' buildings, but also on the value buildings that have reached the end of their lifespan in a circular way. It can even be argued that valuation of the components and materials become most relevant when a building (or component) gets nearer to the end of its financial-economic lifespan. First, because reclamation becomes a realistic option to consider then. Second, because at the beginning of a buildings' lifecycle, the residual value has limited impact on the investment decision because of the discounting factor. And, third, because NPV calculations usually take into account a holding period that is (much) shorter than the financial-economic lifespan of a building, so the residual value of the materials can at best be taken into account indirectly.

In principle, as also discussed in the previous sections, the value of the building at the end of life can be based on the sum of the market values of the (salvageable) components and materials, minus the costs for disassembly/salvation.

For the estimation of the market values of the components, when the decision for disassembly has to be made, several methods can be followed.

In one method, the market value is based on comparison of recent sales or current offers of comparable reclaimed components and materials, similar to how the market value of whole buildings are often estimated. A practical challenge is that there has to be a more or less mature market in order to make sensible comparisons for the valuation.

D4.2 A Set of Methods for Economic and Ecological Appraisal of Circular Economy Innovations

Thus, although in theory correct, the methods described above will encounter practical difficulties in their application and achieving reliable results. For owners who are considering to dispose of a building it is more practical to ask for bids by demolition contractors and other interested parties, even though this will mean that they might not realise the full potential residual value.

Demolition contractors face similar valuation challenges, but have experience with salvaging and selling components and materials from buildings and can therefore make more educated estimations of the residual values. For demolition contractors, the business case is based on the price they expect to get for individual building materials and components in different scenarios: 1) as raw materials for the recycling industry, 2) as products for refurbishment by the (re)manufacturing industry, and 3) as 1:1 reuseable product for the construction industry, also taking into account the extra costs associated with the salvation and temporary storage for each scenario. From a cost perspective, 1:1 reuse becomes worthwhile to consider when the costs for salvation of, refurbishment of and construction with a reclaimed component are lower than the costs of purchasing of and constructing with a new component.

3. Supporting methods for assessing circular potential

For incorporation of the residual value of building components in NPV calculations it is necessary to assess the costs of disassembly as well as the re-use potential. In this chapter we briefly highlight some supporting methods to assess the circular potential, including assessment of the level of disassembly, optimal environmental life time and the condition of building components. Furthermore, we discuss how probabilistic models for life cycle assessment, as explored in Deliverable 1.3 of the Reincarnate project, can be incorporated in financial-economic appraisal

3.1. Level of disassembly

Looking into the valuation of the building components and elements after their lifetime requires specific information to be able to make an informed decision at the end-of-lifetime phase. As elaborated in section 2.4, disassembly costs should be calculated for such assessments. An approach for assessing the disassembly costs on high level can be the categorization of the building classes, which according to standard UNI 8290-1 include super-structures and frameworks, wall systems; window systems; roof systems; floor systems; partitioning. Building systems are made of components that perform specific physical functions and are assembled using either wet methods (e.g., glue, mortar) or dry methods (e.g., bolts, overlaps). These systems are evaluated and scored from 0 to 5 based on their disassembly potential. The average score across all systems determines how easily the building can be dismantled during disposal. Figure 3.1 shows an example of Level of Disassembling (LD) (Fregonara et al., 2017).

Construction Category	Description	LD (Point)
Wet building systems	Building system mainly featured with mortar connections	0
	Building systems mainly featured with glue connections	0
	Building systems mainly featured with jointed connections	0
Reverse assembling building systems	Building systems mainly featured with bolted or riveted connections	3
	Total reversible connections	5

Figure 3.1: Level of Disassembling (LD) score for the building systems analyzed (Fregonara et al., 2017)

3.2. Service life

By focusing on reuse of building components and elements, the estimation of residual service life comes to attention, where service lives should be predicted across multiple uses or building life cycles (Bourke & Kyle, 2019).

One of the aspects of the connection of service life and circular potential is through finding the optimal replacement time for building components when degradation impacts become minimal. In this approach, which is called optimal environmental lifetime (OEL), circular strategies such as Re-manufacturing (with and without upgrade) are considered when a system is replaced. These strategies retain the value of the core product and the reduce the related environmental impact of the production (Hummen & Desing, 2021).

3.3. Condition assessment

NEN 2767-1 “Condition assessment built environment - Part 1: Methodology” provides a methodology to assess the condition of all assets identified in the built environment. By this methodology, the condition of asset’s elements is inspected, and a condition score is calculated ranging from 1 (very good) to 6 (very bad). The results of the condition assessment have potential to provide input for circular, adaptive reuse, or partial disassembly decision making (NEN 2767-1:2017 NI, n.d.).

Platform CB’23 (Platform CB’23, n.d.) has developed a measurement method for circular construction, where the condition score of building elements or construction products is utilized in end of the life cycle decision making. In this methodology, based on the collected data, including the condition scores, multiple indicators for measuring circularity are calculated. These indicators will determine the quantity of materials available for reuse and recycling in the next life cycle in kilograms.

One of these indicators is (indicator 5, shown in Figure 3.2), *degradation at the end of the life cycle*, where the estimated lifespan of objects is taken into account, and the condition scores are used to express the deviation from this lifespan, where:

- Condition score 5 or 6: does not meet requirements or is broken
- Condition score 3 or 4: suitable for a subsequent cycle after some adjustment
- Condition score 1 or 2: meets requirements for a subsequent cycle without any adjustments

D4.2 A Set of Methods for Economic and Ecological Appraisal of Circular Economy Innovations

Figure 3.5: Measuring circularity based on Platform CB'23 Example of picture

3.4. Integration of probabilistic life-cycle assessment

The integration of probabilistic life-cycle assessment (LCA) into economic evaluation frameworks improves the financial and environmental viability of circular economy business models, particularly for reusable construction materials and products. Explored within Deliverable 1.3 of the Reincarnate project, probabilistic methods including Bayesian Networks, Markov Chains, and Machine Learning (ML) approaches the goal of new economic assessments outlined in this Deliverable.

Predictive and probabilistic methodologies directly augment traditional financial appraisal by quantifying uncertainties associated with material reuse potential, durability, and maintenance requirements. Bayesian Networks facilitate real-time updating of probability assessments for structural integrity based on sensor feedback and inspection data, supporting dynamic decision-making processes. Markov Chains model the transition probabilities of construction products between various states of degradation, providing stakeholders with insights into expected service life and necessary intervention schedules.

Machine Learning techniques, informed by historical data and predictive analytics, accurately identify patterns and predictors of degradation, surpassing traditional deterministic models. For instance, ML algorithms effectively forecast deterioration by analyzing historical sensor data, non-destructive test (NDT) results, environmental

conditions, and usage patterns, and doing so they guide maintenance schedules and upgrade interventions. These probabilistic approaches embed risk quantification by definition, and that allows their use within financial models, reducing investment uncertainty.

Economic Benefits: Incorporating predictive life-cycle data into economic appraisal yields several advantages for circular business models in construction:

- **Extending life cycle of buildings.** Probabilistic models like Markov chains, Bayesian networks, and fault tree analysis help engineers anticipate how buildings age and fail, enabling proactive maintenance that extends a structure's lifespan. For example, a Markov chain model applied to hospital roofs in Spain showed it was possible to predict roof degradation and schedule maintenance to delay replacement – effectively extending roof service life by up to 8 years (González-Domínguez et al., 2020). Similarly, integrating Bayesian network algorithms into building information models allows continuous updating of a building's deterioration state with new data, giving planners a decision-support tool for timely repairs and durability management (Morgenstern & Raupach, 2023). Fault Tree Analysis (FTA) adds value by mapping out how small component failures can combine to cause bigger system breakdowns, which helps pinpoint critical weaknesses to fix before they escalate (Bahrami, 2024). Using these probability-based techniques, building managers can shift from reactive fixes to preventive strategies, improving safety and maximizing the usable life of structures. These preventive strategies can then be incorporated in the maintenance planning and budgeting systems, as a basis for cashflow predictions in NPV calculations.
- **Reduced Investment Risk:** Probabilistic modeling provides a clear picture of the *risk distribution* for key outcomes (e.g. how likely a reused component will need early replacement). This transparency allows investors to better gauge the risk-adjusted returns. By quantifying risks (rather than leaving them as unknown), companies can devise mitigation strategies such as warranties, insurance, or maintenance plans, thereby making investments in reuse models less risky. Effective risk management is essential for achieving a high degree of circularity (Chhimwal et al., 2021), and the integrated approach offers exactly that by mapping out where uncertainties lie and how they impact financial performance.

- **Optimized Maintenance and Replacement Schedules:** Predictive models (Markov and ML) help determine optimal timings for maintenance or part replacement to extend life. This prevents both over-maintenance (wasting resources and money by fixing something too early) and reactive break-fix costs (dealing with failures with expensive urgency). To improve the overall life-cycle cost profile of the asset the optimized maintenance may reduce downtime and operational costs. For example, if a probabilistic model shows a high likelihood of failure for a component in year 15, a business can plan a cost-effective refurbishment in year 13-14, avoiding costly failures. Studies in predictive maintenance report significant cost savings and ROI improvements by avoiding unplanned downtime (ATS, n.d.; IOT Analytics, n.d.). In a building context, this means lower life-cycle costs for reusable components, making the circular model more financially attractive.
- **Improved Return on Investment (ROI):** When materials can be kept in use longer and reused in multiple projects, the value extracted from the initial investment increases. By leveraging predictive LCA, companies can maximize the number of reuse cycles for a product (within safe and functional limits) – effectively generating more revenue or service per unit of material. The economic appraisal, enriched with these insights, might reveal higher ROI than a traditional linear model, once the avoided costs of buying new materials and the potential new revenue streams (selling or leasing reclaimed components) are accounted for. Moreover, alignment with sustainability can unlock *green finance* opportunities or incentives (e.g. lower interest loans, sustainability-linked financing), further boosting ROI. In essence, by reducing uncertainty and highlighting value retention, the integrated approach helps prove that circular business models can achieve strong financial performance alongside environmental benefits (Bocken & Geradts, 2022).

Ecological Benefits: Integrating probabilistic assessment into business appraisals also strengthens ecological outcomes and their consideration:

- **Resource Efficiency and Waste Reduction:** A core principle of circular economy is keeping resources in use and eliminating waste (AlJaber et al., 2023). Predictive life-cycle models ensure that this principle is realized by anticipating the *true usable life* of materials and enabling their reuse to the fullest. For instance, if the

model predicts that 80% of concrete elements from a building can likely be reused with minimal refurbishment, the business plan will include recovering and redeploying them, thereby preventing them from becoming waste. This not only conserves raw materials (reducing the demand for new resource extraction) but also diverts substantial volume from landfills. Reincarnate's vision is to reduce construction and demolition waste by up to 80%, and such data-driven planning is key to reaching that target. By integrating these predictions into financial models, companies explicitly account for the savings from waste avoidance (e.g. reduced landfill fees, avoided material purchase) which reinforces the economic case for recycling and reuse.

- **Lower Environmental Footprint:** Probabilistic LCA provides a detailed picture of environmental impacts (carbon footprint, energy use, etc.) across different scenarios. When integrated with economic appraisal, stakeholders can weigh ecological outcomes in investment decisions. For example, a business model scenario that reuses steel beams might show a distribution of potential CO₂ savings compared to using new steel – perhaps a high probability of, say, 50% reduction in emissions. This information can be used alongside financial metrics to choose the scenario that is both viable and green. By predicting likely environmental performance, companies can set more accurate sustainability targets and track them. Moreover, regulatory or carbon pricing risks are better managed: if models indicate a certain probability of high emissions in worst-case scenarios, the business can prepare (or opt for design changes to mitigate that). Overall, the integration promotes decisions that achieve *synergy between economic and environmental goals*, in line with the ethos that in circular construction, financial success goes hand-in-hand with cutting emissions and conserving ecosystems (Bocken & Geradts, 2022).

Better Environmental Forecasting: Traditional LCA often gives a single snapshot of impact. In contrast, probabilistic LCA offers a range (confidence intervals) for environmental impacts under various conditions. By embracing this in the appraisal, firms can do scenario planning for ecological outcomes. For instance, a company can understand the environmental implications if a certain percentage of materials fails to be reused and must be recycled instead. This leads to more robust sustainability strategies – plans that perform well environmentally even in less favorable scenarios. It

D4.2 A Set of Methods for Economic and Ecological Appraisal of Circular Economy Innovations

also improves communication with stakeholders (e.g. communities, regulators, investors concerned with Ecological, Social and Governance criteria), as the business can transparently discuss best- and worst-case environmental outcomes and how it will handle them. Predictive models thus build credibility that the circular business model is not only economically sound but also resilient in delivering ecological benefits.

4. Wider perceptions of value

In the previous chapters, we have explored how circularity can be modelled into NPV calculations for purposes of financial-economic appraisal. In section 2.1 we have pointed out that there is another basic mechanism through which circularity can influence economic value, leading to a premium for investors. In this chapter we discuss the influence of cultural and social factors in perceptions of value and give a brief overview of how circularity is incorporated in some certification systems that can indirectly influence the value attached to buildings by investors.

4.1. Cultural and social factors

Value in the context of circularity is not limited to pure rational calculation of utility. In fact, market valuation of circular and non-virgin materials, products, and components is often influenced by social and cultural biases in relation to second use of resources (Poliportis et al., 2022). As research conducted for Reincarnate's Task T4.1 Adoption of Circular Innovations has shown, circular solutions are often perceived as inferior in quality and durability to *new* solutions, when all other factors are held constant. While in some countries these biases are slowly being overcome for certain products, such as textiles and clothing in platforms like Vinted, these biases are still prevalent in the construction industry, as shown by results of focus groups and interviews in T4.1 and previous research (Geng et al., 2023).

This means that pricing of circular offerings often follows one of two strategies:

1) Price of products and solutions is artificially lowered as an added incentive to stimulate demand, often resulting in a loss for the seller unless supplemented by other sources of revenue or financial incentives (such as state support, see <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/51378e0a-d303-11eb-ac72-01aa75ed71a1>);

2) Price of products and solutions is artificially inflated. From a marketing point of view, pricing these products at a premium, justified by CO2 savings or sustainability claims, for instance, given that the higher price counters perceptions of lower quality among buyers (see <https://business.yougov.com/content/49155-sustainability-premium-53-of-consumers-willing-to-pay-10-extra-for-sustainable-food-and-drink>).

The statements above underscore that valuation of circular solutions may be subject to additional uncertainty when compared to virgin and new solutions, a statement that is backed up by the findings of D4.1 in terms of barriers to the adoption of circular solutions. However, as shown in examples from other sectors, such as textiles and electronics, this uncertainty tends to dissipate as adoption increases, leading to more stable pricing for circular solutions and products. This is especially likely to be the case given the expected resource constraints for construction, which were already evident during events that condition global supply chains such as the COVID-19 pandemic (see <https://www.pmi.spglobal.com/Public/Home/PressRelease/8715c96d2f4645a097a7349f5ed82bb9>). As such, while economic and ecological valuation methods proposed in this deliverable stand on their own, they should also be viewed under the lens of broader social and cultural dynamics that are specific to circularity.

4.2. Circularity appraisal in certification systems

Many (institutional) investors use certification systems to incorporate environmental aspects in their investment decisions. Major certification systems include additional premiums for circular approaches in the building design and construction.

4.2.1. BREEAM

This system gives premium for the efficient use of materials through the life cycle. Projects receive additional credits for adopting innovative design solutions that facilitate end-of-life recycling and materials repurposing. The following aspects are evaluated:

- Measures to minimize the use of materials
- Increasing the proportion of reused materials from demolition
- Use of materials with higher recycled content

The certification also evaluates the durability of materials found in exposed building components, intending to reduce the frequency of their replacement which will result in reducing material consumption. Appropriate protective measures must be taken to prevent damage to internal and external building elements, as described in the evaluation criteria.

D4.2 A Set of Methods for Economic and Ecological Appraisal of Circular Economy Innovations

Possibility of functional adaptation of the building is taken into account through the use of:

- Systems that facilitate the replacement of major installations
- Modular construction
- Possibility of expanding the building vertically or horizontally.

4.2.2. DGNB

This system has introduced a bonus point system for circular measures in the following areas:

- Reusing building materials
- Using recycled materials
- Reducing waste
- Minimizing material inputs
- Increasing building shareability
- Increasing intensity of use.

Improving the environmental performance of heavily contaminated land and implementing systems that allow using greywater or rainwater are separately assessed.

The certification also evaluates:

- Consideration of building adaptation in the context of structural modifications during use
- Origin of materials certified with the appropriate certificates
- Responsible planning for disassembly at the end of the building life.

DGNB is considered as one of the most advanced systems in the context of the implementation of circular economy objectives.

4.2.3. LEED

This system features circular assessment areas and premium point system for implementing measures in this direction.

D4.2 A Set of Methods for Economic and Ecological Appraisal of Circular Economy Innovations

One of the prerequisites to be met in this system is a waste management plan, which can get extra premium for reducing the generation of construction waste to a maximum of 50 kg/m² of building floor area and increasing the level of recovery of materials from construction waste to a minimum of 50%.

Additional premium can be obtained by:

- Reusing historic or abandoned buildings
- Reuse of building components (floors, roofing, walls, doors etc.).

Credits are also awarded in various categories for teams that analyse the supply chain and prevent waste and excess materials before they arrive and procure responsibly-sourced materials.

5. Ecological Appraisal

Adoption of circular economy approaches will depend on their financial-economic viability as well as their environmental benefits. In this chapter, we discuss basic principles of Life Cycle Assessment and Global Warming Potential and how these (can) take into account circularity.

5.1. Life cycle assessment

Life cycle assessment (LCA) has been, since the 1990s, one of the most evolving methods used in the assessment of technologies, products or services and their environmental impact.

It provides a basis for identifying, prioritising and establishing ways to improve environmental quality. In the context of buildings and building products, the most relevant standards are: EN 15978 related to the environmental assessment method for buildings and EN 15804 related to the environmental assessment method for construction products.

LCA is a technique that examines the environmental aspects and impacts of a product throughout its life cycle, reflecting the risks that arise from poorly managed processes in the production of materials, construction and operation of buildings. LCA takes into account all ecosystems and their components, so that the environmental impact of a product can be fully assessed, as well as the consumption of individual environmental resources. The analysis is carried out from the acquisition of the raw material, through the production and use stages, to the end of life. Thanks to this approach, no stage of the product's life is overlooked, making it possible to carry out full analyses of the risks that production of construction materials may pose to the environment.

Sustainable construction is not simply choosing a material or building component with a lower carbon footprint, but looking at how a product will perform in the long term. For example, elements that are highly resilient, have a high coefficient of strength and are easier to adapt and reuse, are a greener choice than products with a lower carbon footprint, but which are less durable, impossible to recycle or reuse. Such a holistic approach is necessary for the complete decarbonisation of the construction sector.

5.2. Global warming potential and abiotic depletion potential

The carbon footprint of a building or a product is the sum of all greenhouse gas emissions associated with processes occurring during its life cycle. The value of the carbon footprint is directly linked to the Global Warming Potential (GWP) indicator expressed in kilograms of CO₂ equivalent (kgCO₂e). The carbon dioxide equivalent includes the impact of emissions of various greenhouse gases, not just CO₂, but it is commonly referred to as carbon dioxide emissions, which should be taken as a simplifying abbreviation.

Substance	Atmospheric lifetime (years)	GWP ₁₀₀ (kg CO ₂ e)
Carbon dioxide (CO ₂)	-	1
Methane (CH ₄)	12 (on decomposition in the atmosphere, CO ₂ remains)	23
Nitrous oxide (N ₂ O)	144	296
Sulphur hexafluoride (SF ₆)	3200	22 200
Carbon tetrafluoride (CF ₄)	50000	5700

Table 5.1: GWP values according to Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (Bartosz, Kowalski 2022)

According to Level(s) guidelines, reporting of the global warming potential expressed in kgCO₂e should take into account its origin from fossil sources, biogenic sources, and from land use and land use change. GWP is the most common used measure of environmental impact of a product.

Several building projects (UKGBC, 2022) have already used circular economy principles and are able to evidence associated reductions in carbon. This impact was most clearly seen through the reuse principle, and a range of impacts on financial and nonfinancial value were also identified. This demonstrates that circularity benefits not just carbon reduction, but a much broader set of organisational, social, environmental, and financial aspects. However, to fully assess the environmental quality of a given material, its Abiotic Depletion Potential (ADP) should also be considered, providing comprehensive information on the rarity of a given material or its components. ADP is used as

environmental impact indicator of EN 15804, used as guidance on generation of the Environmental Product Declaration (EPD).

The Abiotic Depletion Potential (ADP), used in environmental analyses, can be used to measure the weight of individual materials. It is determined based on individual raw materials' consumption and global resources, which are related to a reference resource, antimony (Sb). It determines the potential for depletion of non-renewable resources (i.e., minerals, oil, natural gas, metals) due to the extraction and processing of resources needed to produce a given material (Pikoń et al., 2022). ADP considers the quantity and quality of the resources consumed and their potential renewal time. The higher the ADP for a given material, the greater the depletion of the Earth's natural resources and, thus, the greater the burden on the environment.

Using the indicator of mineral depletion (ADP) makes it possible to evaluate quantitatively and qualitatively. By analogy with economic analysis, we can say that ADP is a measure of value, a kind of „environmental price” of a given material. For example, suppose we use two materials and want to determine their value. In that case, we have to have information on their quantity (e.g. kg) and unit price (i.e. related to the volume of the material, e.g. EUR/kg). Similarly, in the case of circularity assessment, knowledge of quantities of individual substances is not enough. We need to consider both the quantities of material (e.g., kg) and their „unit environmental price,” which is ADP (expressed in kg Sb/kg) (Pikoń et al., 2022).

The primary objective of circularity is to conserve primary raw materials, making it crucial to distinguish between recycled, downcycled, and reused materials. Recycling typically involves applying technological processes, such as the preparation of materials, which often require electrical energy to grind aggregates sourced from demolished buildings. This energy consumption further necessitates the use of raw materials for its generation. On the contrary, if materials are reused, for instance, in the form of finished components, there is no need for extensive adaptations. Structural steel beams are a prime example of such reuse, as they can be directly utilized without any modifications. Therefore, acknowledging the disparities between reuse, recycling, and downcycling becomes vital in the assessment process of circularity.

5.3. Whole life carbon and building life cycle stages

In European guidelines for LCA (EN 15978), the entire building life cycle is made up of 15 modules assigned to the three main stages of the cycle:

- A - upfront carbon - product and construction processes
- B - embodied carbon in use phase and operational carbon
- C – end-of-life carbon.

The product stage includes modules A1 (raw materials supply), A2 (transport) and A3 (manufacturing). Further modules related strictly to the construction process are A4 (transport of products to the construction site) and A5 (construction process).

Within the use stage, life cycle modules related to the permanent components of the building such as B1 (use), B2 (maintenance), B3 (repair), B4 (replacement), B5 (refurbishment) and modules related to the utilities supplied to the building, namely B6 (energy consumption) and B7 (water consumption), have been identified.

The four modules associated with the end-of-life stage are C1 (deconstruction/demolition), C2 (transport of debris and waste), C3 (waste processing) and C4 (waste disposal or storage).

The analysis may also include module D, which considers any greenhouse gas emissions (or reductions) that occur outside the life cycle of the building under consideration, which can be linked to the possibility of reusing building components in a new facility, or recycling them.

The carbon footprint of a building can be determined for different life cycle ranges:

- *From cradle to gate*, which covers **modules A1 to A3** - only emissions associated with the manufacture of products from which the building is or will be constructed are considered.
- *From cradle to completion* takes into account **modules A1 to A5** - it additionally includes emissions caused by the transport of products to the construction site and by the construction process itself. The carbon footprint estimated for this range is called upfront carbon.

D4.2 A Set of Methods for Economic and Ecological Appraisal of Circular Economy Innovations

- *From cradle to grave*, where the entire life cycle of the building should be taken into account, thus **modules A1-A5, B1-B7 and C1-C4**. The results of this assessment give the figure of the total carbon footprint. However, it is worth noting that within the total carbon footprint there is additionally a distinction between the operational carbon, associated with modules B6 and B7, and the embodied carbon, associated with the other life cycle modules.
- As work on the transition to a **circular economy progresses**, also *cradle-to-cradle* assessments, that additionally take into account the environmental benefits and loads of **module D** are also gaining importance, thus they can be considered optionally.

	A1-A3	A4-A5	B1-B3	B4-B5	B6-B7	C1-C4	D
LCA modules	Extraction and transport of raw materials and production	Product transport and construction	Operation, maintenance and repair	Replacement and refurbishment	Energy and water consumption	Demolition and transport of waste and its disposal or treatment	Benefits and loads beyond the building life cycle
LCA stages	Product stage	Construction process stage	Use stage			End-of-life stage	

Figure 5.1: Building life cycle phases by module according to EN 15978:2012 (Bartosz, Kowalski 2022)

5.4. CO2 reporting on waste management

The CO2 Report is a digital value-added service from Reincarnate partner Ragn Sells that provides clients with detailed and verified climate data related to their waste management. The report translates complex environmental impacts into concrete figures in the form of carbon dioxide equivalents (CO₂e) - a key tool for companies seeking to meet the increased requirements of the EU's Corporate Social Responsibility Directive (CSRD), the GHG Protocol or other internal monitoring needs. The report also includes information on recycling rates and treatment methods, providing an overall

D4.2 A Set of Methods for Economic and Ecological Appraisal of Circular Economy Innovations

picture of resource flows and climate impacts. The report starts with customers registering their waste via Ragn Sell's digital customer portal, where each material collected is recorded by weight and volume. Based on this data, a CO₂e report is automatically generated showing both the climate impact (scope 3, category 5 of the GHG protocol) and the fate of the material according to ESRS E5-5. The report is available for download and is continuously updated. The service helps clients save time and resources by providing ready-made and easy-to-use climate calculations - ready for use in sustainability reporting. It also provides greater insight into the climate impact of their operations and how increased recycling can reduce the need for virgin raw materials. By showing avoided emissions and resource flows, it gives customers the tools to improve both their environmental performance and their bottom line.

Figure 5.2: The CO₂e report covers emissions associated with facilities and transport according to the system boundaries of the GHG Protocol scope 3 category

5.5. Integrating LCA and LCC

LCA quantifies environmental and economic impacts over the life cycle. In the construction sector, these impacts are calculated in terms of Embodied Energy, and Embodied Carbon. The synergy of LCA and LCC can provide insight for evaluating different scenarios with circular potential.

By integrating LCC and LCA, the research adopts a life cycle management (LCM) (shown in Figure 5.3) perspective that supports long-term decision-making. The combination of economic and environmental aspects is shown to be complementary in residential development—lower energy use leads to reduced operational costs (Ristimäki et al., 2013).

Figure 5.3: Three pillars of sustainability

D4.2 A Set of Methods for Economic and Ecological Appraisal of Circular Economy Innovations

To integrate the environmental and economic indicators, the Global Cost method is developed to express both of these indicators in monetary terms. The LCA indicators, and environmental indicators in end-of-life are monetized as shown in Tables 5.2 and 5.3.

Environmental Indicators in End-Of-Life	Unit	Cost Items
Level of disassembly of building systems	points	Dismantling costs
Recycled materials quantity	%	Disposal costs (waste disposal costs—Value of recycled materials)
Wastes production quantity	Kg	

Table 5.2: Environmental indicators in end-of-life stage and relative cost items (Fregonara et al., 2017)

Environmental Indicators	Unit	Cost Items
Embodied Energy	MJ	Cost of electric power
Embodied Carbon	kg CO2 eq (100 years)	Cost of Carbon tax in Europe

Table 5.3: Embodied Energy and Embodied Carbon indices and relative cost items (Fregonara et al., 2017)

These costs can be summed up to Global Cost as follows:

$$C_{CGEnEc} = C_1 + C_{EE} + C_{EC} + \sum_{t=1}^n (C_m + C_r)/(1+r)^t + (C_{dm} + C_{dp} - V_r)/(1+r)^n$$

C_{CGEnEc} = Life Cycle Cost including environmental and economic indicators [€]

C_1 = investment costs

C_{EE} = costs related to Embodied Energy

C_{EC} = costs related to the Embodied Carbon

C_m = maintenance costs

C_r = replacement costs

C_{dm} = disassembly costs

C_{dp} = disposal costs

D4.2 A Set of Methods for Economic and Ecological Appraisal of Circular Economy Innovations

- V_r = residual value
- t = period in which the cost occurred
- n = number periods considered for the analysis
- r = discount rate

As in the CE-LCC method described in section 2.3, this can be further extended to incorporate multiple life cycles. For instance, a new attributional life cycle inventory model, grounded in the value retention process (VRP) framework of the circular economy, was developed to quantify life cycle inventories and assess environmental impacts across multiple stages—from in-community separation to end-of-use and beyond into subsequent lifecycles. The VRP framework is based on R9 strategies (Zhang et al., 2024) and visualised in Figure 5.4 below. Examples of application of similar approaches to LCA and LCC in the built environment can be found among others in Eberhardt et al. (2020), Stijn et al. (2022) and Wouterszoon Jansen et al. (2022).

Figure 5.4: Circular economy in the material flow and lifecycle stages of kerbside waste material loop process (Zhang et al. 2024)

6. Integration into CP-IM

The RE LCC tool, as an application of RE Suite, enables the integration of economic data into BIM models, facilitating cost analysis within a BIM environment. It can automatically associate cost categories, allowing for rapid life-cycle cost (LCC) assessments of various renovation strategies.

Designed for BIM-based LCC computations, the RE LCC tool relies on open formats like IFC to extract geometric information. By linking to a cost database, it enables LCC evaluations across multiple time frames and user-defined variables such as inflation and discount rates. It also includes a BIM viewer for visualizing the building model

RE LCC supports economic assessments over a specified analysis period to inform decision-making, compare alternatives, evaluate investment scenarios, estimate future costs for budgeting, and assess investment feasibility (see Figure 7.1).

Figure 7.1: LCC module of the CP-IM

In the context of circular economy potential, the RE LCC tool offers several use cases. One short-term use case involves guiding decisions around small-scale replacements and end-of-life interventions, helping users determine whether individual components should be replaced, refurbished, or disposed of based on cost and sustainability criteria. In the long term, the tool supports strategic planning by incorporating the reuse value

of materials, such as glass, into the overall cost analysis—encouraging design choices that retain material value and reduce waste. Furthermore, the integration of the RE Condition Assessment provides condition scores that can inform evaluations of circular potential. By assessing the physical state of building elements, this feature supports informed decisions about reuse, refurbishment, or replacement, further aligning LCC with circular economy principles. These use cases are elaborated further below.

6.1. End-of-lifetime Implementation in LCC

Circular construction tends to be more costly because it often involves using alternative materials instead of standard steel and concrete, along with increased labour expenses from employing unconventional or innovative building methods. Nevertheless, when choosing materials during the design phase, it's important to weigh these upfront costs against the potential savings during the building's operational and end-of-life stages. As a result, life cycle costing (LCC) plays a crucial role in assessing the total expenses of various circular construction options across all stages of the building's life cycle (Rajagopalan et al., 2021).

BIM can provide comprehensive information which helps the decision-making process regarding the end of a building life cycle (AlJaber et al., 2023). An example would be the decision between reuse, repair, or recycle of building materials and components. In Reincarnate, by utilizing the ontologies developed for circular processes such as glass recycling, the building model can be queried about the quantity of recyclable glass in a building, and connected to that, the LCC module can estimate the NPV for different circular scenarios (such as landfilling, partial recycling, full recycling).

Additionally, as described in section 5.5, LCA methodology can be integrated with LCC. This combined approach allows for a more holistic evaluation of both economic and environmental impacts of circular interventions at the end-of-life stage.

The pipeline depicted in Figure 7.2 illustrates how BIM, circular ontologies, and LCC can be integrated to guide end-of-life interventions and small replacements.

Figure 7.2: integration of BIM, circular ontologies, and LCC to guide end-of-life interventions

6.2. Condition Assessment Integration

Building on the methodologies of NEN 2767-1 and Platform CB'23 (as described in section 3.3), a condition-based decision pipeline can be developed to support short-term circular interventions. This approach integrates condition scores of building components with LCC to guide decisions such as reuse, repair, or replacement in a cost-effective and circular manner. This condition score integration pipeline enables stakeholders to make data-driven, circular decisions on short-term replacements, linking technical viability with financial sustainability (see Figure 7.3).

Figure 7.3: Condition score implementation pipeline

7. Conclusion

In this report, Deliverable 4.2 of the Reincarnate project, we have discussed a set of methods for financial economic and ecological appraisal of circular economy innovations in buildings. We have focussed in particular on how residual (end-of-use cycle) values of building components can be incorporated in Net Present Value calculations which are commonly used by investors to support their decisions from a financial-economic perspective. Moreover, we have discussed that wider cultural and social considerations influence the value that is attached to circularity in buildings. Incorporation of circularity in certification systems helps (institutional) investors to attach premiums to the value of circularity in buildings. Additionally, separate ecological appraisal remains necessary, because environmental ‘externalities’ (negative effects caused by our building construction, use, maintenance, renovation and demolition) are not fully incorporated in standard NPV calculations. Some innovative approaches have been developed to incorporate financial and ecological appraisal from a circular (multi use cycle) perspective. However, these methods incorporate a lot of assumptions about lifespans, costs for disassembly and remanufacturing and resale values of building components. This is partly inherent to appraisal of buildings, being ‘fixed’ assets with a long lifespan, and partly due to the immature state of the market for reclaimed building components. This makes it unattractive for investors to rely on these theoretically more sophisticated models and leads us to the following recommendations:

- Continue to collect data in a (hopefully) maturing market, to improve data availability and reliability, so it will make sense to use the more sophisticated models in due time;
- In the meantime, do incorporate circularity and adaptive re-use in financial-economic appraisal of buildings and components a couple of years before a major investment decision about renovation or disposition. This already makes sense from a financial-economic as well as ecological point of view;
- Reinforce ecological appraisal in addition to financial-economic appraisal as a key factor in decision making for construction, renovation, maintenance and disassembly of buildings, adopting a whole life (multiple use) cycle perspective on a wide range of ecological effects (looking beyond carbon emissions).

D4.2 A Set of Methods for Economic and Ecological Appraisal of Circular Economy Innovations

To demonstrate how to determine the expected financial-economic outcome towards the end-of-use cycle at building component level, we will employ Reincarnate's test case of the re-use of single glass (as also referred to in section 2.4). We will add cost information to the circular value flow planning as described for re-use of single glass in Deliverable 1.4. The costs of remanufacturing single glazing to double glazing can then be benchmarked against the costs of new double glazing to see if re-use is competitive from a financial-economic point of view.

References

- AlJaber, A., Alasmari, E., Martinez-Vazquez, P., & Baniotopoulos, C. (2023). Life Cycle Cost in Circular Economy of Buildings by Applying Building Information Modeling (BIM): A State of the Art. *Buildings*, 13(7), 1858. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13071858>
- ATS (n.d.) "Predictive Maintenance Cost Savings | ATS." Accessed: Apr. 01, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.advancedtech.com/blog/predictive-maintenance-cost-savings/>
- Bahrami, M., Roghani, B., Tscheikner-Gratl F. & Rokstad M.M. (2024) "A deep dive into green infrastructure failures using fault tree analysis," *Water Research*, vol. 257, p. 121676, doi: 10.1016/j.watres.2024.121676
- Bartosz D. & Kowalski W. (2022). Estimating the Carbon Footprint of Buildings
- Bocken, N. M. P., & Geradts, T. H. J. (2022). Designing Your Circular Business Model. *Stanford Social Innovation Review*, 20(2), 34–39. <https://doi.org/10.48558/3NZN-SZ76>
- Bourke, K., & Kyle, B. (2019). Service life planning and durability in the context of circular economy assessments—Initial aspects for review. *Canadian Journal of Civil Engineering*, 46(11), 1074–1079. <https://doi.org/10.1139/cjce-2018-0596>
- Chhimwal, M., Agrawal, S., & Kumar, G. (2021). Measuring Circular Supply Chain Risk: A Bayesian Network Methodology. *Sustainability*, 13(15), 8448. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13158448>
- Conijn, J.B.S. (1995). Enkele financieel-economische grondslagen van de volkshuisvesting, Delft, Onderzoeksinsituut OTB. <http://resolver.tudelft.nl/uuid:ec8eb1c7-bef0-4abd-b9b7-735390cf4ffc>
- Eberhardt, L. C. M., van Stijn, A., Rasmussen, F. N., Birkved, M., & Birgisdottir, H. (2020). Development of a life cycle assessment allocation approach for circular economy in the built environment. *Sustainability*, 12(22), Article 9579. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12229579>
- European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (2021). Incentives to boost the circular economy: A guide for public authorities (Independent Expert Report). Publications Office of the European Union. https://doi.org/10.2777/794570_op.europa.euhoop-hub.eu
- Fregonara, E., Giordano, R., Ferrando, D. G., & Pattono, S. (2017). Economic-Environmental Indicators to Support Investment Decisions: A Focus on the Buildings' End-of-Life Stage. *Buildings*, 7(3), Article 3. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings7030065>

Geng, J., Huang, Y., Li, X., & Zhang, Y. (2023). Overcoming barriers to the adoption of recycled construction materials: a comprehensive PEST analysis and tailored strategies. *Sustainability*, 15(19), 14635

González-Domínguez, J., Sánchez-Barroso, G. & García-Sanz-Calcedo J. (2020). "Preventive maintenance optimisation of accessible flat roofs in healthcare centres using the Markov chain," *Journal of Building Engineering*, vol. 32, p. 101775, doi: 10.1016/j.jobbe.2020.101775

Hummen, T., & Desing, H. (2021). When to replace products with which (circular) strategy? An optimization approach and lifespan indicator. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 174, 105704. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105704>

IHS Markit & Chartered Institute of Procurement and Supply (2021). Strong increase in construction output; costs rise at fastest pace since survey began in 1997 (UK Construction PMI®) [Press release]. S&P Global.

IOT Analytics (n.d.). "Predictive maintenance market: 5 highlights for 2024 and beyond." Accessed: Apr. 01, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://iot-analytics.com/predictive-maintenancemarket/https://www.pmi.spglobal.com/Public/Home/PressRelease/8715c96d2f4645a097a7349f5ed82bb9>

Morgenstern H. & Raupach M. (2023). "Predictive BIM with Integrated Bayesian Inference of Deterioration Models as a Four-Dimensional Decision Support Tool," *CivilEng*, vol. 4, no. 1, Art. no. 1, doi: 10.3390/civileng4010012

NEN 2767-1:2017 nl. (n.d.). Retrieved April 10, 2025, from <https://www.nen.nl/en/nen-2767-1-2017-nl-227639>

Pikoń K., Bogacka M., Landrat M. & Piecha-Sobota K. (2022). A Guide to Circularity in Construction.

Platform CB'23. (n.d.). Platform CB'23. Retrieved April 10, 2025, from <https://platformcb23.nl/>

Polyportis, A., Mugge, R., & Magnier, L. (2022). Consumer acceptance of products made from recycled materials: A scoping review. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 186, 106533.

Ristimäki, M., Säynäjoki, A., Heinonen, J., & Junnila, S. (2013). Combining life cycle costing and life cycle assessment for an analysis of a new residential district energy system design. *Energy*, 63, 168–179. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2013.10.030>

Simeon, L. (2024). Sustainability premium: 53 % of consumers willing to pay 10 % extra for sustainable food and drink. YouGov. <https://business.yougov.com/content/49155->

D4.2 A Set of Methods for Economic and Ecological Appraisal of Circular Economy Innovations

[sustainability-premium-53-of-consumers-willing-to-pay-10-extra-for-sustainable-food-and-drink](#)

Stijn, A. van, Eberhardt, L. C. M., Wouterszoon Jansen, B., & Meijer, A. (2022). Environmental design guidelines for circular building components based on LCA and MFA: Lessons from the circular kitchen and renovation façade. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 357, Article 131375. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.131375>

UKGBC (2022). Insights on how circular economy principles can impact carbon and value Wouterszoon Jansen, B., van Stijn, A., Eberhardt, L. C. M., van Bortel, G., & Gruis, V. (2022). The technical or biological loop? Economic and environmental performance of circular building components. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 34, 476-489. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2022.10.008>

Zhang, J., Bhuiyan, M., Zhang, G., & Sandanayake, M. (2024). Life cycle assessment of kerbside waste material for an open-looped and closed-loop production– towards circular economy designs. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 434, 139991. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.139991>

Zwueste, A. (2023). Evaluating Circular Real Estate - Determine the value of circular real estate using a DCF-model, Delft, Delft University of Technology